

ISic3489

I.Sicily inscription 3489

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8726

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Θ(εοῖς)] Κ(αταχθονίοις)
2. [---]λιος Κλώδις [---]
3. [---]ς οὔνομα Φίλοσφ[---]
4. [---]κυσ ἐνθάδε κεῖται[---]
5. [---]ει πάντα Ρ[---]
6. [---]ιωπλου[---]
7. [---]υ,σ[---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645110

EDR 140897

EDCS 41300113

PHI 175756

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 151

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3489. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358592>